

ISRU IN THE CISLUNAR VALUE CHAIN: AN EXAMINATION OF ISRU TECHNOLOGY DEVELOPMENT ALIGNMENT WITH INTERNATIONAL LUNAR SCIENCE AND EXPLORATION CAMPAIGNS.

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Introduction: ISRU is widely cited as an enabling lunar capability need, from construction of lunar habitats to refueling. However, most examinations of ISRU technology development in the broader cislunar value chain focus on end infrastructure goals, rather than the ability to meet intermediate science and exploration objectives. Firefly's recent announcement of the development of Ocula, the first commercial lunar imaging and mapping service available, opens a new lunar market, while other applications, such as hosted payloads on technology demonstration missions may also achieve science objectives. This presentation examines cislunar science and exploration campaigns funded by international governments as well as in the private sector, and identifies how ISRU technology developments or products may help enable goals for future missions. This analysis is informed by the results of a scenario workshop with the ISRU community exploring potential lunar architecture futures with varying levels of ISRU capability development and investment. It additionally highlights where ISRU technology development timelines may align with existing mission timelines and goals.

Background: Recent lunar planning increasingly treats ISRU as a staged set of activities that begin with prospecting, environmental characterisation, and small-scale technology demonstrations. NASA's Lunar Surface Innovation Initiative explicitly frames ISRU as a pathway towards producing water, fuel, and other supplies from lunar materials, whilst also advancing excavation and construction capabilities needed for sustained surface operations. ESA has articulated a similar logic, linking a sustainable return to the Moon with commercial delivery services, communications support, and technologies that can turn indigenous materials into oxygen and water. At the mission level, NASA's Commercial Lunar Payload Services (CLPS) programme is especially significant, because it purchases delivery services from commercial providers for science and technology payloads, creating intermediate opportunities to test mobility, drilling, sample handling, navigation, and dust-mitigation systems before full ISRU architectures are built. Long-running orbital missions already support this phased approach: NASA's Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter has mapped the Moon since 2009 and continues to inform landing site selection, resource assessment, and exploration planning. As such, the proposed analysis examines ISRU as an incremental capability stack that will firstly generate

value through exploration-enabling services, data products, and hosted technology demonstrations. More broadly, these developments can be situated within an emerging cislunar circular economy, in which native resource use, reusable infrastructure, and reduced waste are central to sustainable lunar exploration.

Case Studies: Firefly's Ocula provides a useful case study for this market framing. Firefly describes Ocula as a commercial lunar imaging and mapping service to be deployed on its Elytra orbital vehicles, beginning no earlier than late-2026. According to Firefly, the service will use high-resolution ultraviolet and visible-spectrum telescopes to support mineral identification, higher-fidelity landing-site mapping, and cislunar situational awareness. Ocular is particularly relevant, because it extends a broader model in which commercial transportation and operations infrastructure is being used to support science and technology customers. For example, Firefly's Blue Ghost Mission 1 landed on the Moon in March 2025 under NASA's CLPS initiative and carried 10 NASA science and technology payloads, including demonstrations related to sub-surface drilling, regolith acquisition, precision navigation, and dust mitigation. Comparable patterns are visible elsewhere, including NASA's PRIME-1 mission, which paired resource prospecting objectives with a commercial lander delivery, whilst commercial rover platforms, such as Lunar Outpost's MAPP and Astrobiotic's CubeRover are being positioned as flexible vehicles for mapping, resource detection, and hosted payload operations. Taken together, these efforts suggest that lunar imaging, prospecting, and shared mobility/data services may become meaningful precursor markets that de-risk subsequent ISRU deployment whilst still advancing near-term science and exploration objectives.

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